

TACC Core Experience Portal

- A robust open-source platform for building custom science gateways without starting from scratch
- Aggregates systems, services, APIs, and storage into a single, unified interface for researchers
- Offers a dashboard for real-time data storage, application execution, and job monitoring
- Integrates user storage with TACC's high-performance systems, simplifying data management
- Facilitates rapid deployment of new gateway projects with shared, customizable features

<https://cep.tacc.utexas.edu> | <https://github.com/TACC/Core-Portal>

